

QUADRAT DATA SHEET

Site:

Date:

Observers:

Q#	Seagrass present? (Y/N)	Morphotype(s)	%Total cover	Height (cm)	Animals seen (tick)	Notes
1			<input type="checkbox"/> 0% <input type="checkbox"/> 1-25% <input type="checkbox"/> 25-50% <input type="checkbox"/> 50-75% <input type="checkbox"/> 75-100%		<input type="checkbox"/> Fish <input type="checkbox"/> Crab <input type="checkbox"/> Sea cucumber <input type="checkbox"/> Starfish <input type="checkbox"/> Shell <input type="checkbox"/> Other	
2			<input type="checkbox"/> 0% <input type="checkbox"/> 0-25% <input type="checkbox"/> 25-50% <input type="checkbox"/> 50-75% <input type="checkbox"/> 75-100%		<input type="checkbox"/> Fish <input type="checkbox"/> Crab <input type="checkbox"/> Sea cucumber <input type="checkbox"/> Starfish <input type="checkbox"/> Shell <input type="checkbox"/> Other	
3			<input type="checkbox"/> 0% <input type="checkbox"/> 0-25% <input type="checkbox"/> 25-50% <input type="checkbox"/> 50-75% <input type="checkbox"/> 75-100%		<input type="checkbox"/> Fish <input type="checkbox"/> Crab <input type="checkbox"/> Sea cucumber <input type="checkbox"/> Starfish <input type="checkbox"/> Shell <input type="checkbox"/> Other	
4			<input type="checkbox"/> 0% <input type="checkbox"/> 0-25% <input type="checkbox"/> 25-50% <input type="checkbox"/> 50-75% <input type="checkbox"/> 75-100%		<input type="checkbox"/> Fish <input type="checkbox"/> Crab <input type="checkbox"/> Sea cucumber <input type="checkbox"/> Starfish <input type="checkbox"/> Shell <input type="checkbox"/> Other	

OBSERVATIONS

Check	None	Low	Medium	High	Notes (where? what did you see?)
Physical damage (anchor scars, prop marks, trampling, mooring circle)					
Seagrass flowers or fruit present? Species/morphotype (if known) + where					
Pollution (plastic, fishing line, debris)					
Water color					
Other observations					

Question	Team / group answer
Total quadrats completed	
Quadrats with seagrass present (count)	
Most common % cover class	
3 animals observed (most interesting)	1) 2) 3)
1 sign of stress or threat observed	
1 positive sign of a healthy meadow	